

EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS ON INVESTMENT PATTERN OF PROFESSIONAL WOMEN IN UDUMALPET, TAMILNADU

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Abstract:

Investment is employment of funds with the aim of the achieving additional income growth in value. The essential qualities of and investment are that it involves waiting for a reward. It involves the commitment of resources, which have been saved or put away from current consumption in the hope that some benefits will accrue in future. Investment is the allocation of monetary resources to assets that are expected to yield some gain or positive return over a given period of time. Investment is the sacrifice of certain present values for the uncertain future reward. Investment entails arriving at numerous decisions relating to type, mix, amount, timing and grading of investment. An investment decision is a tradeoff between risk and return. All investment choices are made in accordance with the personal investment ends and in contemplation of an uncertain future.

Key Words: Investment Pattern, Annual Saving & Behavioral Finance

Introduction:

Investment is employment of funds with the aim of the achieving additional income growth in value. The essential qualities of and investment are that it involves waiting for a reward. It involves the commitment of resources, which have been saved or put away from current consumption in the hope that some benefits will accrue in future. Investment is the allocation of monetary resources to assets that are expected to yield some gain or positive return over a given period of time. Investment is the sacrifice of certain present values for the uncertain future reward. Investment entails arriving at numerous decisions relating to type, mix, amount, timing and grading of investment. An investment decision is a tradeoff between risk and return. All investment choices are made in accordance with the personal investment ends and in contemplation of an uncertain future. Investments are both important and useful in the context of present day condition

Statement of the Problem:

The nineties is undoubtedly the decade of women. Today's women have scaled every peak, both literally and figuratively. It is this transformation in the social science that has enables women to right take their place as contributing partners in the work place, pouring into the economy an immense flow of brainpower and energy. Despite the progressive attitudinal change, it is significant to note that barely 1/3 of the total working population are women. Traditionally the careers for women have been largely in the hospitality sector, in personal services as air host uses or beauticians, in teaching, catering, selling and clerical jobs, where the intrinsic personal qualities of women are among the requirement for the career. But in recent years, women have pushed. For greater challenges, making progressively bigger strides in enlarging the scope and ambit of these careers. In old days, the investment decisions were only in the hands of men, but now a day's women can also participate, as they are mostly employed. The important of investment decision is enhancing by the fact that there is an increasing number of working in organization. These women will be responsible for planning their own investment, during their working life. The investment pattern of professional women investors will depends upon their skills, knowledge and their income.

Objectives of the Study:

- The study has been carried on with the following objectives
- ✓ To study the various pattern of investment in the study unit.
 - ✓ To analyze attitude of women investors and its impact on investment.

Methodology

A sample constituting 100 investors, belonging to different part of Udumalpet Town was selected for the purpose of the study. Udumalpet town is representing various socio- economic groups of investors from all levels of people. The sample of the study was drawn from the universe applying purpose sampling techniques. "Purpose sampling is where the researcher has the power to select or reject any term in an investigation". The choice of the sample depends upon the judgment of the investigator. The data required for the study was collected by way of questionnaire. A pilot study was conducted among women investors and find out the inconvenience in filling up the questionnaire and also identify unnecessary questions. Based on the information collect from the pilot study, the present questionnaire was formulated. The survey was administrated by way of issuing questionnaire to the women investors, as study was to be completed within a period of six month. Necessary instruction was given to the women investors by the researcher while filling up the questionnaire the collected data was reformulated into master table.

Discussion and Analysis:

To know the nature and character of investor concerned under the study, the general profile in terms of age, marital status, education qualification, occupation, annual income, annual savings, total investment held as on date, number of family members, number of earning members and number of dependent were studied to increase the reliability of the study. The samples were classified and then tabulation was made. The hundred respondents are taken for the study. These samples are analyzed and interpreted. Tables are drawn on the basis of percentage method.

Table 1: Distribution of respondents based on type of investment

S.No	Type of Investment	Respondents	Percentage
1.	Heavy risk	18	18
2.	Moderate	53	53
3.	Risk free	29	29
Total		100	100%

Source: Primary Data

The above table reveals that 18% of professional women respondents choose heavy risk investment, 53% of respondents were in moderate risk, and 29% of respondents choose risk free investment. From the above table we infer that most of the professional women investors choose the moderate risk. This shows that women are encouraged to take risk to invest their funds outside.

Table 2: Distribution of respondents based on annual savings of investors

S.No	Annual Savings	Respondents	Percentage
1.	Below Rs. 2,500	20	20
2.	Rs. 2,501 to 5,000	24	24
3.	Rs. 5001 to 7,500	32	32
4.	Rs. 7501 to 10,000	24	24
Total		100	100%

Source: Primary Data

The above table represents the savings of women investors, out of the respondents 20% of the respondent's save below Rs.2,500, 24% respondents annual savings is between Rs. 2,501 to 5,000, 32% respondents annual savings lies between Rs. 5,001 to 7,500 and 24% respondent's savings amount is between Rs. 7,500 to 10,000. From the above table we infer that investors or respondents annual savings lies between Rs. 5,000 to Rs. 7,500 this shows the saving habit and awareness for future among the respondent.

Table 3: Distribution of respondents based on utilization of investment

S.No	Regular Investor	Respondents	Percentage
1.	Own Savings	33	33
2.	Family Savings	36	36
3.	Business Income	9	9
4.	Borrowings	5	5
5.	Capital Gain	9	9
6.	Inherited Property	8	8
Total		100	100%

Source: Primary Data

The above table indicates that 33% women respondents have been utilizing their own savings for investment, 36% women respondents utilize family member savings, 9% respondents use their business income for investment, 5% respondents use borrowed funds for investment, 9% respondents utilized for capital gain, 8% of women respondents utilize their inherited properties for investment. From the above table we infer that most of the women respondents utilized their own savings for the investment.

Table 4: Distribution of respondents based on preference of present investment

S.No	Basis of preference	Respondents	Percentage
1.	Tax Relief	13	13
2.	Safety And Security	22	22
3.	Profitable One	20	20
4.	Stability Of Income	15	15
5.	Future Return	16	16
6.	Cash Need Any Time	10	10
7.	Others	4	4
Total		100	100%

The above table represents that 13% respondents savings provides tax relief, 22% respondents investment provides safety & security, 20% respondent choose investment which is profitable one, 15% women respondents prefer investment based on the stability of income, 16% women respondents savings give certainly of future return, 10% respondents told that investment has satisfied their at any time cash need, 4% women

respondents invest because of other reasons. From the above table we infer that most of the women respondents prefer investment for stability of income and certainly of future return. This helps for their future commitment and to plan for future.

Major Findings:

- ✓ Most of the professional women investors are below the age of 25 years.
- ✓ Majority of the professional women investors are married.
- ✓ Most of the investors are held their total investment between Rs. 50,000 to Rs. 1,00,000.
- ✓ Majority of the professional women investors gather the sources of information in newspaper.
- ✓ Many of the professional women investors prefer medium term gains.

Suggestions:

- ✓ The following are the suggestion made with the help of the study.
- ✓ Awareness programmes have to be conducted by the government to create and awareness relating to various type of investment.
- ✓ Government may provide a separate scheme of investment to the women investors.
- ✓ Women investors most take the financial decisions with the consultant of other family member.
- ✓ Today's life woman involves the all work and others.
- ✓ Today middle class people women's will involve the investment sector.
- ✓ Women investors' family could make up 2 earning members.

Conclusion:

This paper is a reflection of the behaviour of various categories women investors. Selection of a perfect investment avenue is a difficult task to any investor. An effort is made to identify the preferences of a sample of investors selected from large population. Despite of many limitations to the study I was successful in identifying some investment patterns, there is some commonness in these investors and many of them responded positively to the study. This report concentrated in identifying the needs of present and future investors, investor's preference towards various investment avenues are identified based on their income. Investors risk in selecting a particular avenue is dependent on the age of that investor. This study confirms the earlier findings with regard to the relationship between Age and risk tolerance level of individual investors. Women are less likely to take investment risks for whatever reason many women are less willing than men to take risks. The Present study has important implications for investment managers as it has come out with certain interesting facets of an individual investor. The women investor still prefers to invest in financial products which give risk free returns. This confirms that Indian investors even if they are of high income, well educated, salaried, independent are conservative investors prefer to play safe.

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